

Television Broadcasting and Mental Health Campaigns in Nigeria

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Abstract

Irrespective of the increasing prevalence of mental health disorders, responses within the Nigerian media remain inconsistent, poorly structured and largely insufficient to address cultural misconceptions and stigma. This study, therefore, explored the role of television broadcasting in advancing mental health campaigns in Nigeria. Drawing on framing theory as propounded by Erving Goffman, the study underscored how the framing of mental health content shapes public perception and societal attitudes. This paper contends that television broadcasting holds immense, but underutilised potential in advancing mental health campaigns. Given its reach, accessibility and emotional influence, television can serve as a deliberate and coordinated tool for reshaping narratives, fostering social change and driving sustained advocacy in mental health discourse across Nigeria.

Keywords: Television, Mental Health, Nigeria, Public Perception

Background to the Study

Mental health has become a public health concern globally with serious implications for individuals, families and national development. In Nigeria, the burden of mental health disorders is rising, yet public awareness remains limited due to prevailing cultural taboos, social stigma, and insufficient information dissemination. The World Health Organisation (2022) estimates that nearly one in every four Nigerians may be affected by a mental or neurological disorder during their lifetime, yet access to care is extremely limited. In a nation where mental health is still misunderstood by many, using television to educate the public can help challenge false beliefs and encourage compassion. Television can help normalise discussions around mental health and make people realise that it is okay to ask for help.

Baran (2019) states that television broadcasting is a form of mass communication that has the power to affect how people think and feel about important issues in society. It plays a big role in shaping public opinions and attitudes. One reason for this is because television uses moving images, sounds and spoken words, which makes it easier for people to understand and connect with the message being shared. Unlike newspapers or books that require reading skills, television can reach a wider audience, including those who may not be able to read or write. This makes it useful in countries like Nigeria, where literacy levels vary. Television brings information directly into people's homes in

a way that feels immediate and real. People can see real-life situations, hear personal stories, and watch experts explain complex health issues in a simple way.

Gureje, Lasebikan, Ephraim-Oluwanuga, Olley & Kola (2015) explain that mental health discourse in Nigeria has historically been shrouded in silence, misconceptions and religious attributions. Many Nigerians perceive mental illness as a spiritual problem rather than a medical condition, thereby contributing to the marginalisation of affected individuals. This perception is worsened by the lack of structured educational campaigns, particularly in mainstream media. As such, the few public health messages on mental well-being are often buried within broader health discussions or poorly presented without sustained programming. Umeh (2020) argues that television broadcasting in Nigeria is regulated by the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), which mandates stations to dedicate a portion of airtime to public interest programming. However, much of this programming focuses on political, economic or general health issues, with mental health receiving little attention. As Umeh notes, despite Nigeria's growing media space, mental health narratives are rarely integrated into regular content and when they are, they are sometimes misrepresented through stigmatising portrayals in dramas and news reports. This lack of targeted and informed broadcasting limits public understanding and reinforces negative stereotypes.

Furthermore, the role of television in health communication is anchored on the agenda-setting theory, which posits that mass media have the power to influence the salience of issues in the public domain. By choosing what to broadcast and how frequently, television broadcasters shape what the public considers important. When mental health issues are underreported or distorted, they fall off the national agenda, leaving critical awareness gaps. Thus, the framing and frequency of mental health content in television programming become key concerns for researchers, media practitioners and policymakers alike (Asemah 2016). The neglect of mental health in Nigerian media is also shown in national health strategies. According to Olayiwola & Adeleke (2019), the Nigerian government allocates less than 4% of its total health budget to mental health and communication plans for public awareness are minimal. This indicates that television could serve as an accessible and cost-effective platform to provide accurate mental health information, highlight available support services, and promote positive attitudes. However, this potential remains largely untapped.

That aside, in recent years, there have been calls for the Nigerian media to become more socially responsible by promoting developmental communication that addresses pressing health challenges, including mental health. Scholars like Nwabueze (2020); Asemah (2019) have noted that the media have a duty to inform, educate and mobilise the public on issues of social importance like mental health. Given the reach and influence of television in rural and semi-urban communities, media campaigns targeting mental health can have far-reaching impacts if well designed and consistently aired.

Statement of the Position

This study takes the position that television broadcasting in Nigeria holds immense potential in advancing mental health campaigns and should be deliberately harnessed as a

strategic tool for public education, stigma reduction and behavioural change. Given its reach, accessibility and emotional influence, television stands as a powerful medium capable of reshaping the narrative around mental health in a society still entrenched in cultural misconceptions and silence surrounding mental illness. Irrespective of the growing prevalence of mental health disorders in Nigeria, media responses, most especially on television have remained inconsistent, poorly structured and largely insufficient. The position advanced in this paper aligns with the agenda-setting theory (Asemah, 2016), which posits that the media have the capacity to influence what the public perceives as important. Television broadcasters can play a transformative role in addressing public ignorance, fear, and discrimination against mental health sufferers by placing mental health at the centre of national discourse through consistent, accurate and culturally sensitive programming.

Furthermore, this position recognises that public health communication is a shared responsibility among stakeholders, including the government regulators, broadcasters, medical professionals and civil society organisations. It is, therefore, imperative that the Nigerian television industry assumes a proactive role in designing and broadcasting mental health content beyond crisis moments or observance of international health days. Sustained programming, drama integration, talk shows and expert interviews must be adopted as long-term strategies to normalise conversations around mental health and promote a culture of help-seeking. Hence, this study defends the position that Nigerian television should not remain on the sidelines in the mental health movement. Rather, it must be repositioned as a central actor in national mental health advocacy, with deliberate policy support, professional training and strategic content development driving this transformation. Therefore, this study is situated within the intersection of public health and media studies, as it seeks to examine television broadcasting and mental health campaigns in Nigeria

Theoretical Framework

Framing theory was first propounded by Erving Goffman in 1974. Goffman introduced the idea that people interpret and give meaning to social reality based on frames, which are structures that help individuals organise and understand events. Later, Robert Entman (1993) expanded on this foundation within the field of media and communication, as he provided a more structured perspective on how media content can influence public perception by selecting and emphasising certain aspects of reality.

The framing theory posits that the way information is presented (framed) affects how audiences perceive and respond to it. In media practice, framing involves the deliberate construction of messages to highlight specific angles, narratives or meanings. For instance, television broadcasts may choose to frame mental illness as a medical condition requiring support and treatment, or alternatively as a burden or source of danger. Each frame invites a different understanding and reaction from viewers, shaping societal attitudes and potentially reinforcing or challenging prevailing stigmas. Entman (1993) identified four core functions of framing that constitute its central tenets; these include: defining problems-identifying what an issue is and its causes; diagnosing causes-

explaining who or what is responsible; making moral judgments-offering ethical evaluations of the issue and actors involved and suggesting remedies, which implies providing possible solutions or courses of action. These components work together to shape public discourse and guide social action. Television broadcasters, therefore, hold considerable influence in shaping not just public awareness but also collective response to mental health issues through the frames they adopt.

The framing theory is appropriate for this study because of its capacity to explain how Nigerian television influences public perception of mental health. Given that many Nigerians rely on television as a key source of information, the frames embedded within news reports, health features or drama programmes can either normalise mental health discourse or perpetuate harmful stereotypes. By applying framing theory, this study aims to critically evaluate how mental health narratives are structured within Nigerian television content and the extent to which these representations promote awareness, reduce stigma or reinforce bias. The theory provides a valuable framework for assessing the power of television in constructing public meaning and influencing behavioural change regarding mental health.

Role of Television Broadcasting in Mental Health Campaigns in Nigeria

Television broadcasting plays an important role in shaping public discourse, influencing perceptions and driving behavioural change across societies. In Nigeria where mental health issues are deeply misunderstood and often stigmatised, television stands as a potentially transformative tool for raising awareness, educating the public and promoting positive mental health practices. Its visual and auditory capacity, emotional impact and wide reach makes it an effective platform for delivering health messages to diverse audiences (Gureje *et al* 2015).

Baran (2019) explains that one of the most significant roles television plays in mental health campaigns is in public education. Through documentaries, talk shows, interviews with mental health professionals, drama series and public service announcements, television can inform viewers about the nature of mental illnesses, their symptoms, causes and available treatment options. As noted by the author,

Media serve as key agents of socialisation, who provide knowledge that shapes attitudes and beliefs. In a society where mental illness is usually linked to spiritual causes or moral weakness, television has the power to present scientifically accurate and culturally sensitive narratives that challenge these myths.

Umeh (2020) notes that another important role television plays is normalising conversations around mental health. Representation matters in shaping how individuals perceive themselves and others. When mental health issues are portrayed in mainstream media content such as in popular soap operas, films and current affairs programmes, it can help reduce stigma, increase empathy and encourage affected individuals to seek help. A consistent media representation of mental illness in a non-threatening and humanising way is a key factor in breaking the cycle of discrimination and shame. Also, television broadcasting can serve as a mobilisation tool that can prompt individuals,

families and communities to take action. By highlighting real-life stories of recovery, profiling mental health initiatives and promoting mental wellness campaigns, TV stations can inspire viewers to access services, support affected loved ones, and participate in advocacy. This role is vital in rural areas and among populations with limited access to digital media, where television may be the only source of formal education and information, (Olayiwola & Adeleke, 2019).

Television also serves a policy advocacy function. When used strategically, it can draw attention to mental health as a national priority, pressuring policymakers to fund mental health services, implement supportive legislation, and integrate mental health into primary healthcare systems. This aligns with the development communication approach, which views media as partners in addressing societal problems (Nwabueze, 2015). Furthermore, the agenda-setting function of television is very powerful. As proposed by McCombs & Shaw (1972), media do not tell people what to think, but what to think about. In Nigeria, where mental health tends to receive minimal attention in mainstream news cycles, frequent and prominent television coverage can increase the salience of the issue and influence how it is discussed in public and private spheres. This includes the potential to guide conversations during national events such as World Mental Health Day, elections or healthcare reform debates.

Contribution of Nigerian Television Broadcasters to Mental Health Campaigns

Nigerian television broadcasters have made some modest contributions toward mental health awareness, albeit in a manner that is largely fragmented, inconsistent and reactive rather than proactive. While the responsibility of public enlightenment falls within the mandate of broadcast institutions as defined by the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), mental health has not enjoyed the same level of attention as other public interest issues like politics, corruption and general physical health concerns. Nonetheless, certain national and private television stations have occasionally incorporated mental health themes into their programming, offering some foundational groundwork for broader engagement (WHO, 2020).

As described by Olaywiola & Adeleke (2019) national broadcasters such as the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) and state-owned stations have aired occasional public service announcements and documentary-style programmes during major health observances like World Mental Health Day. These broadcasts typically feature health experts who speak briefly on depression, anxiety or substance abuse. However, these efforts are often event-based, lacking sustained follow-up or integration into long-term programming. As observed by Olayiwola & Adeleke such isolated media interventions have minimal impact when they are not sustained or repeated frequently enough to influence public knowledge and attitudes.

Umeh (2020) argues that private broadcasters like Channels Television, TVC News and AIT have also contributed through short health segments, interviews and panel discussions in their morning or weekend shows. For example, Channels Television's *Health Matters* has occasionally featured discussions on mental well-being in relation to stress, suicide and substance use among youth. These segments, however, are infrequent and usually lack in-depth analysis, audience interaction or follow-up reporting. What this

implies is that the general framing of mental health in Nigerian private broadcast media is still largely reactive driven by tragic events such as celebrity suicides and crises in psychiatric institutions, rather than pre-emptive educational engagement. Anwar & Malik (2020) contend that some local television dramas and soap operas such as those produced in collaboration with non-governmental organisations (NGOs) have attempted to incorporate mental health issues into their storylines. Notably, organisations like Mentally Aware Nigeria Initiative (MANI) and She Writes Woman have partnered with content producers to address depression, trauma and schizophrenia within entertainment narratives. However, these efforts are still limited in scale and often not backed by the broadcasting stations themselves. Rather, they are independent creative efforts that depend on external funding and may not be replicated across different stations or regions. Also, training and capacity-building initiatives for broadcasters on mental health reporting are still relatively rare. Many television journalists and content creators in Nigeria have not received formal training in health communication, let alone mental health-specific reporting. This results in unintentional misrepresentation, sensationalism or use of derogatory language when mental health stories are covered in news bulletins or feature reports. As Akinfeleye (2020) rightly observes, the media cannot properly inform the public on issues they do not fully understand or appreciate. Hence, for television broadcasting to fully realise its potential in mental health advocacy, there must be a deliberate shift from occasional coverage to structured, consistent and professional content development driven by policy, training and collaboration.

Gaps and Limitations in Television Broadcasting of Mental Health Campaigns in Nigeria

Despite the growing relevance of mental health in Nigeria's public health discourse, its coverage in television broadcasting remains inadequate and inconsistent. Although, in the 21st century, television holds immense potential to raise awareness and influence public attitudes, several gaps and limitations tend to hinder its effectiveness in promoting mental health campaigns. These shortcomings span from structural, professional, institutional, to content-related dimensions. It also shows a disconnect between public interest broadcasting and the urgency of mental health education (Chibueze, 2020).

As Olayiwola & Adeleke (2019) observe, a notable gap is the lack of sustained programming dedicated to mental health. Most Nigerian television stations only air mental health content occasionally and when they do, it is tied to special events such as World Mental Health Day or following a high-profile tragedy. This episodic approach prevents the consistent reinforcement of key messages needed to influence long-term behavioural change. Without regular and repeated programming, mental health education cannot penetrate public consciousness or displace entrenched myths and stigma. Melanie, Wakefield, Barbara & Hornik (2018) state that another limitation is the inadequate training of broadcast professionals on mental health reporting. Many Nigerian television producers, reporters and presenters lack the technical knowledge required to handle mental health topics with the nuance and sensitivity they deserve. As a result, mental health is either neglected entirely or misrepresented using sensationalist language, stereotypical portrayals or stigmatising visuals. Some TV news reports still refer to persons with mental illness as "mad" or "lunatic." This shows a deep-seated lack of understanding within the media industry itself.

Furthermore, there is a scarcity of expert-led programming. Gureje *et al* (2015) contend that while entertainment and current affairs dominate Nigerian television schedules, few stations allocate time for expert panels, documentaries and educational programmes that are focused on mental well-being. Where such programmes do exist, they are usually poorly funded, aired at off-peak hours and presented in a format that fails to engage diverse audiences. As the authors point out, meaningful public education on mental health must involve specialists, psychiatrists, psychologists, and trained counsellors, who can provide accurate and actionable information.

Nwabueze (2020) asserts that structural limitation lies in the commercial orientation of most television broadcasters, most especially private ones. Private stations are driven by advertising revenue and viewer's ratings. This makes many stations to prioritise content that attracts mass appeal, such as politics, sports and entertainment. Mental health is viewed as a niche or "unpopular" topic, due to the perception that it will not generate sufficient audience interest. Nwabueze argues that this commercial bias undermines the developmental role of the media and contributes to the neglect of socially important but commercially "unattractive" issues like mental health. There is also a geographical and linguistic gap in mental health broadcasting. Most available mental health content is produced and broadcast in English and largely targets urban audiences. This alienates rural populations and non-English speakers who may also face mental health challenges but are left uninformed due to language and accessibility barriers, (Agency for Health Care Research and Quality, 2014).

Institutionally, the absence of clear policy directives and enforcement mechanisms limits broadcasters' accountability in promoting mental health awareness. Although the National Broadcasting Code mandates public interest programming, it does not explicitly require mental health coverage as part of broadcasters' responsibilities. Without clear guidelines, broadcasters are not compelled to invest in the development and airing of mental health campaigns. This regulatory ambiguity allows stations to neglect the subject without consequences.

Counterarguments and Refutations

It has been noted that television plays a vital role in advancing mental health awareness. While this is well acknowledged, some critics argued that television is no longer the most effective medium for public health campaigns in Nigeria. With the rise of social media platforms and the growing preference among young people for digital content, some researchers contend that television may have a diminishing influence, especially among urban youth populations. They argued that the interactive and personalised nature of online media makes it a more suitable tool for engaging audiences on sensitive issues like mental health (Ibrahim, 2021).

Another counterpoint raised by sceptics is that many Nigerian television stations lack the editorial independence or funding to run sustained and impactful mental health campaigns. These critics suggest that due to political or commercial pressures, media houses often prioritise entertainment or government-driven agendas over socially relevant issues (Eze, 2022). Also, where mental health is featured, it is sometimes done inaccurately or sensationally, reinforcing stigma rather than dismantling it. There is an argument that many Nigerian television journalists and content producers lack the requisite training to handle mental health topics professionally. Without proper

knowledge and sensitivity, broadcasters may present mental illness in a manner that reinforces negative stereotypes. Anozie (2020) notes that popular Nollywood-inspired television dramas depict mentally ill characters as violent, cursed or socially deviant. This misrepresentation breeds fear and misunderstanding rather than compassion and support. Hence, television may unintentionally contribute to misinformation and negative stereotypes.

However, these arguments overlook the broad reach, credibility and influence that television still maintains in both rural and urban areas. The National Bureau of Statistics (2023) confirms that television remains one of the most trusted sources of information in both urban and semi-urban areas. Stations such as TVC News and NTA have been instrumental in health education campaigns on topics like HIV/AIDS and COVID-19, which demonstrates their capacity to influence public knowledge and behaviour when properly harnessed. Also, the argument that television lacks interactive capacity is being countered by the increasing integration of social media and digital feedback into broadcast formats. Programmes such as Health Matters on Channels TV and Wellness Half Hour on Lagos Television now combine traditional broadcast with real-time audience interaction via SMS, WhatsApp and Twitter. This hybrid model makes television a more dynamic and responsive platform, capable of engaging diverse demographics, including tech-savvy youth (Nwachukwu, 2022).

Therefore, the solution is not to discard television broadcasting but to strengthen its content, funding, and partnerships with mental health professionals and regulatory bodies. With strategic policy support, sustained investment, and inclusive programming, Nigerian television can be repositioned as a vital instrument in the national mental health campaign. Dismissing it would mean forfeiting a powerful, far-reaching medium that is deeply woven into Nigeria's social fabric.

Conclusion

Mental health has gradually emerged from the peripheries of public discourse in Nigeria to become a growing national concern. As this study has established, the rising rates of mental health disorders, compounded by poverty, insecurity, cultural stigma and systemic neglect, necessitate a coordinated awareness campaign. Television broadcasting due to its wide accessibility, cultural relevance and visual power, remains an invaluable tool for driving mental health education and advocacy across the country. Despite the criticisms against television as an outdated or underperforming medium, the evidence presented here reaffirms its unique potential to reshape public attitudes. Nigerian broadcasters such as Channels Television, NTA, TVC and even state-owned stations have shown growing interest in addressing social issues, but their commitment to mental health remains inconsistent and sometimes superficial. What is needed is a deliberate and strategic use of television content through documentaries, panel discussions, drama series, PSAs and news segments that accurately inform the public while reducing long-held myths and prejudices against those living with mental health conditions.

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